

PEDAGOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES AND DIDACTIC CONDITIONS OF CREATIVITY DEVELOPMENT IN FUTURE TECHNOLOGICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS

N.N.Utaeva

National Institute of Educational Pedagogy named after T.N. Kori Niyozı doctoral student

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13985600>

Abstract. *This article is about the didactic conditions for the development of creativity in teachers of advanced technological education.*

Keywords: *creative, technological education, didactic conditions, activity, component, logical thinking, competence.*

Nowadays, pedagogical activity and preparation for it is considered as the acquisition of professional functions based on the development of knowledge, skills and abilities. The demands of the rapidly changing times, the critical thinking of today's learners, the independent search and finding of information, the development of intellectual work culture, and the skills of independent learning are among the urgent tasks of modern education. Modern education, like all fields, requires speed, effective adaptation to rapid changes in a short period of time, active assimilation of new knowledge on the basis of existing disciplines, and consistent familiarization of students with them. From this point of view, it is necessary to create certain didactic conditions for the development of creativity in future teachers of technological education. These conditions should be aimed at developing creative thinking and problem-solving abilities of teachers during the educational process, and should expand their opportunities to use innovations in their future pedagogical activities.

At this point, let's first talk about the pedagogical conditions. Based on the scientific foundations presented in pedagogical sources, it is not an exaggeration to say that "pedagogical conditions" are the conditions for the implementation of the pedagogical process using educational technologies, methods, forms, tools, and approaches [1].

Pedagogical condition is a component of designing a pedagogical system that describes the influence of conditions-internal and external factors [2]

The pace and level of modern development is determined by the environment of high competition according to the standards set in social, pedagogical and other systems. This process can be changed in the definition of pedagogical conditions, taking into account modern trends. As a result of studying the results of many studies and scientific-pedagogical analysis during our scientific research, we present the following information about the concepts of pedagogical conditions.

In pedagogy, conditions are often understood as a set of factors, circumstances, and measures on which the effectiveness of the pedagogical system depends: A.S.Belkin, L.P.Kachalova, E.V.Korotaeva, L.M.Yakovleva believe that pedagogical conditions help the development of the pedagogical system.

N.M.Boritko understands the course of the pedagogical process as a situation in which the teacher consciously develops a significant effect in order to achieve a certain result [3].

V.I.Andreev considers pedagogical conditions to be "the result of purposeful selection, design and application of content elements, methods (techniques), as well as organizational forms to achieve the goal" [4].

Thus, a number of experts expressed their opinions about the organizational and pedagogical conditions for the development and implementation of educational processes and cited information about the achievement of the effectiveness of the quality of education in this process.

Effective development of creative activity of future technology teachers requires implementation in certain pedagogical conditions. According to the Russian scientist V.I.Andreev, "Pedagogical conditions are conditions of the educational process that are the result of purposeful selection, design and application of content elements, methods, and organizational forms to achieve certain didactic goals".

As a result of observing the process of organization of technology classes using the relevant sources of literature and information sources and various information sources within the framework of our scientific research work, we came to the conclusion that the presence of the following pedagogical conditions is important in developing the creativity of future technology teachers. came.

Pedagogical conditions	Legal regulation:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Content: Laws, regulations and rules governing the educational process. These documents allow the organization of activities of educational institutions, the determination of the rights and obligations of teachers and students, and the implementation of the teaching process. • Significance: The legal normative framework ensures the legitimacy of the educational process and regulates it, which increases the quality and sustainability of education.
	Scientific and pedagogical support:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Content: Scientific justification of education and training processes, conducting pedagogical research, development and implementation of innovative educational methods. • Significance: Scientific-pedagogical support allows to improve the educational process based on the scientific approach and ensures effective use of modern pedagogical theories and methods.

Material supply:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Content: The material and technical base of the educational institution, including classrooms, workshops, laboratories, sports halls, libraries and other infrastructure facilities, as well as educational tools and equipment. • Importance: Material support is necessary for the full implementation of the educational process and the effective organization of students' learning. These conditions increase the quality and efficiency of teaching.
Methodological supply:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Content: Methodological manuals, textbooks, training programs, materials and resources necessary for the implementation of the educational process. • Significance: Methodological support helps teachers to organize their activities efficiently, helps to make lessons interesting and meaningful. These conditions allow students to be deeply involved in the learning process.
Technological support:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Content: Optimization of the educational process, with the help of technological support, the educational process is conducted consistently and systematically. Conducting interactive lessons increases the interest of students in the lesson. Visualizing learning materials using technology helps learners understand complex concepts more easily. Evaluation and analysis capabilities. • Significance: Increasing efficiency, individualized learning opportunities, support for creativity and innovation, global and multifaceted learning, and sustainable and systematic learning process all guarantee the quality of education.

These conditions are necessary for the successful organization of the educational process and the effective work of future technology teachers. Each component is interrelated, and their harmony serves to increase the quality of education. Also, in the development of the creative activity of a technology teacher, he should have the following skills: set theoretical tasks, guide students to find different ways out of difficult situations using different methods; interest them in creative activities; organization of creative work during practical training on technology; taking into account the individual characteristics and interests of students, it is necessary to be able to adequately use teaching methods and pedagogical technologies that ensure mastery of the methods of changing the objects of work to achieve the goal.

The creative activities of the technology teacher include the use of his higher cognitive capacities (eg, problem solving, logical thinking), as well as motivational and value-based inspiration of students. In this process, while uncovering personal inclinations and possibilities, it may include the following methods:

Innovatsion yondashuvlar: Texnologiya o'qituvchisi yangi texnologiyalarni qo'llash orqali ta'lim berish metodlarini yangilashi va o'quvchilarning qiziqishlarini kuchaytirishi kerak. Masalan, virtual reallik, sun'iy intellekt yordamida interaktiv darslar tashkil etishi.

Innovative approaches: A technology teacher should update teaching methods and increase students' interests by using new technologies. For example, organizing interactive lessons using virtual reality, artificial intelligence.

O'zaro hamkorlikni rivojlantirish: O'quvchilarni guruh bo'lib ishlashga undash, ularga bir-biri bilan bilim va g'oyalarni almashish imkoniyatini berish

Development of mutual cooperation: Encourage students to work in groups, give them the opportunity to share knowledge and ideas with each other

Muammoli vaziyatlar yaratish: O'quvchilarga murakkab muammolarni, loyihalarni hal qilish imkoniyatini berish orqali ularning mantiqiy fikrlash va ijodiy yechimlar topish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishi

Creating problematic situations: Difficult problems for students. to develop their logical thinking and problem-solving skills by giving them opportunities to solve projects

Considering the social and cultural context: Understanding the different cultural and social backgrounds, values and motivations of students and tailoring lessons accordingly.

Encourage students to: Identify each student's individual interests and inspire them based on that, such as modeling or project-based learning.

Such creative approaches of the technology teacher ensure that students actively participate in the learning process and acquire new knowledge and skills. This is important not only for learning, but also for personal and social development.

In the course of the research work, it was confirmed that the correct and effective performance of practical training in the field of specialization is important for the development of the creativity of future technology teachers.

During our scientific research, attention was paid to the analytical rationality of studying the level of development of creative activity of future technology teachers. It is important to include analytically sound criteria in the study and assessment of creative activities of future technology teachers. Below are the main criteria for evaluating this activity:

№	ACTIVITY	SKILLS	COMPETENCES
1.	Scientific and practical activity:	Research Skills: How students conducted scientific research, how they analyzed research results and how they applied them to practice. This criterion evaluates the teacher's ability to conduct scientific work.	Practical experience: The level of the student's practical application of scientific theories in teaching activities, organization and conduct of laboratory and experimental work.
2.	Production technological activity	Management of technological processes: The teacher's knowledge of production technologies, their effective management of production processes and problem solving.	Contact Industry: Practical experience of the teacher in the field of production and relations with industry in the organization of technological processes.
3.	Project activity	Project works: The teacher's ability to create and implement a project, including design, preparation of technical documents, setting project deadlines and manage the resources.	Creative solutions: The ability to find and apply new and innovative solutions in the project process, to demonstrate a creative approach within the project.
4.	Experimental research skills	Experimental research skills: The teacher's ability to conduct experimental research, plan experiments and analyze the results.	Testing innovative technologies: Testing new technologies and evaluating their effectiveness.

5.	Technical qualifications and skills	Tool skills: Ability to work with modern technological equipment, their effective use and maintenance.	Technical thinking: The teacher's ability to analyze technical problems and find innovative solutions for them.
6.	Pedagogical skill and creativity	Application of pedagogical methods: The teacher's ability to creatively use various pedagogical methods and methods, the level of involvement of students in the learning process.	Creating innovative materials for lessons: The teacher's development and use of new, creative teaching materials for classes.
7.	Ability to make decisions and solve problems	Overcoming challenges: Overcoming technological or educational challenges through creative approaches.	Independent decision-making: O'qituvchining mustaqil qarorlar qabul qilish va ularni amaliyotda muvaffaqiyatli qo'llashi.
8.	Communication and teamwork skills	Ability to work in a team: Effective teacher collaboration with other teachers, students, and industry representatives.	Creativity in communication: Use of creative approaches in expressing different opinions and cooperation.

These criteria serve as a basis for evaluating and developing creative activities of future technology teachers. Through these criteria, it is ensured that teachers have not only theoretical knowledge, but also practical skills, technological and pedagogical skills.

The conclusion is that the development of creativity in teachers of future technological education is carried out through the purposeful and effective organization of the pedagogical process. When a number of pedagogical opportunities and didactic conditions are combined, the process of developing the creativity of future technological education teachers will be effective and they will become qualified specialists with innovative pedagogical approaches.

REFERENCES

1. Андреева, Л. А. Дидактические игры как средство развития профессионально значимых качеств будущего специалиста: дисс. ... канд. пед. наук: 13.00.08 / Л. А. Андреева – Орел, 1999. – 228 с. Анненкова, Н. В. Педагогические условия формирования практической готовности будущего учителя как субъекта воспитательной деятельности [Текст] / Н. В. Аннекова // Учение записки. Электронный журнал Курского государственного университета. – 2008. – № 4. – С. 39–45
2. Динин, С. А. Современные подходы к определению сущности категории «педагогические условия» [Текст] / С. А. Динин, Б. В. Куприянов // Вестник Костромского гос. ун-та им. Н.А. Некрасова. – 2001. – № 2. – С. 101–104
3. Борытко Н. М. В пространстве воспитательной деятельности. Волгоград: Перемена, 2001
4. Андреев В. И. Педагогика: Учебный курс для творческого саморазвития. Казань: Центр инновационных технологий, 2000. 124 с